

Spectrophotometric and Conductometric Studies of the Complex between Fe(III) Ion and 2-Hydroxy-3-naphthoic Acid in Aqueous Medium

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Fe³⁺ ion forms a blue, water-soluble complex with 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid with maximum absorbance at 570 m μ . The pH range of constant maximum absorbance is between 2.3 and 3.1. The molecular extinction coefficient is 2.33×10^3 . The formula of the complex, established spectrophotometrically and conductometrically is FeR (R=reagent). The dissociation constant of the complex, as calculated from Job's method and mole-ratio method at 30°, is 0.804×10^{-5} and 0.981×10^{-5} , respectively, whereas the free energy of formation of the complex is -8.945 kcal./mole at 30° from the latter method.

2-Hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid forms a blue, water-soluble complex with Fe³⁺ in acidic medium. The complex is formed almost instantaneously and the colour intensity remains unaltered even after 12 hours at the room temperature. The complex shows maximum absorbance at 570 m μ where the absorption by the reagent is negligible.

As no data are available in the literature on the above complex, the nature and composition of the complex have been determined spectrophotometrically, using Job's method of continued variations¹, slope-ratio method², and mole-ratio method³. The formula of the complex has been confirmed by conductometric studies. The dissociation constant of the complex has also been determined.

EXPERIMENTAL

A pure solution of ferric chloride was prepared from ferrous ammonium sulphate⁴ (B.D.H., A.R.) and the iron content was estimated by the oxide method before preparing the standard solutions. 2-Hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid (R) was a B.D.H. pure sample and was recrystallised before use. Hydrochloric acid and sodium acetate used were of B.D.H. AnalaR quality.

Absorbance measurements were made by a Hilger Uvispec spectrophotometer (Model H700-308 of Hilger Watts Ltd., London) using 1 cm effective light path. Conductometric measurements were made, using a conductivity meter (type LBR, manufactured by Wissenschaftlich-Technische Werkstätten, Germany) and pH by a Beckman pH-meter (Model H2). All the experiments were done at a constant temperature of $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$.

1. *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, **2**, 9, 113.

2. Harvey and Manning, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4488.

3. Yoe and Jones, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1944, **16**, 111.

4. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans Green & Co. Ltd., 3rd ed., 1962, p. 470.

Spectral Studies.—Ferric chloride solution and the reagent solution (5 ml of $M \times 10^{-3}$ each) were taken in a 25-ml flask. Suitable quantities of 1.0*N*-HCl and 1.0*N* sodium acetate were added so that the pH after dilution was at 2.6. The complex showed the maximum absorbance at 570 μ which was used as a suitable wave length for all subsequent work.

Effect of pH.—Solutions containing the same concentrations of ferric chloride and the reagent were prepared at different pH values and their absorbance was noted at 570 μ . The range of constant maximum absorbance was from pH 2.3 to 3.7.

Nature of the Complex.—Mixtures containing varying proportions of ferric ion to reagent were prepared and the absorbance at different wave lengths in each case was measured. In all the cases, the maximum absorbance occurred at 570 μ , thus indicating formation of only one complex with the reagent responsible for the colour⁵.

Composition of the Complex

Job's Method.—A series of equimolecular solutions was prepared from $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ of the metal and the reagent in which the ratios of metal to reagent varied from 1:9 to 9:1, keeping the pH in each case at 2.6. Absorbance was measured at 570 μ . Curve 1 in Fig. 1 illustrates the results by applying this method. The maximum at 5:5 ratio of the Fe(III) to the reagent indicates the formation of FeR . The same ratio of Fe(III) to the reagent was also obtained by starting with $0.5 \times 10^{-3} M$ of metal and the reagent (curve 2, Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. By Job's method.

Fig. 2. By slope-ratio method.

1: Fe(III) varying. 2: Reagent varying.

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Slope-ratio Method.—The concentration of the variable component was varied from $2.5 \times 10^{-3} M$ to $2.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ in presence of the excess concentration of $5 \times 10^{-3} M$ of the constant component. The pH of the solutions was maintained at 2.6. Fig. 2 shows the measured absorbance at 570 m μ plotted against the concentration of the variable component. The slopes of the two straight lines provide Fe(III) to the reagent ratio as 1 : 1.

Mole-ratio Method.—A series of solutions (10 ml) was prepared from $1.25 \times 10^{-3} M$ of the reagent and $0.5 \times 10^{-3} M$ metal at pH 2.6. Varying concentrations of the metal ($0.5 \times 10^{-3} M$) was added to the fixed amount of the reagent ($1.25 \times 10^{-3} M$) so that the mole ratio of the reagent to Fe(III) was from 1:0.2 to 1:6. Fig. 3 shows a break at a ratio of one mole of the reagent to one mole of the metal.

Conductometric Method.—Fig. 4 shows the titration curves of $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ and $0.5 \times 10^{-3} M$ reagent with ten times concentrated solutions of ferric chloride, respectively. From these curves also the ratio of the reagent to metal is found to be 1:1 which confirms the formula of the complex obtained by spectrophotometric measurements.

Fig. 3. By mole-ratio method.

Ferric chloride (ml).

Fig. 4. By conductometric method.
1: 40 ml of $0.5 \times 10^{-3} M$ reagent vs. $0.5 \times 10^{-3} M$ ferric chloride.
2: 40 ml of $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ reagent vs. $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ ferric chloride.

The dissociation constant of the complex found by mole-ratio method at 30° is 0.981×10^{-5} . Hence the stability constant is 1.020×10^5 . Molecular extinction coefficient, ϵ , is equal to the slope of the straight line in which ferric chloride is varying. From Fig. 2

Its value comes to be 2.30×10^3 at 570 m μ . The standard free energy ΔF° of the complex is found to be -6.945 kcal./mole at 30° from the mole-ratio method.

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